

Ancient Indian Temple Towns and its Sustainable Planning Strategies

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Abstract

In Ancient India, temples were not only the places of worship, but important places for social life, social trades and for community activities. It also shows how religion, architecture, local trade and urban planning were brought together. This study shows how the temple town planning strategies of Srirangam balanced both design and sustainability together. What are the facts and principles behind the balanced planning. This traditional ideas are still useful today. Concepts like walkability, neighbourhoods, energy-efficient buildings, water-sensitive planning, mixed land use, passive cooling techniques etc. This can guide modern urban design to create cities that are sustainable and connected to culture.

Key features: Walkable streets, climate-responsible design, natural cooling, water management systems, mixed-land use, temple based economic activity in temple buildings

1.Introduction

1.1. Background of temple towns

Temple towns were developed around the important temples and became more than just places of worship. They became the sources of living for the local people, where social, cultural and economic activities took place. The temple usually formed the centre of the town, with streets, markets homes and waterbodies arranged around it. In places like Srirangam, the layout shows a clear order of how these design elements like streets, pathways, public spaces were designed both for religious and daily life purposes. These were also planned as per the climate, using shaded streets, open spaces, waterbodies to keep the environment comfortable. The long-lasting structures show how they thoughtfully planned and built knowledge of these traditional communities.

1.2 Research Problem

Apart from the sustainable design and historical importance, temple towns are often overlooked in modern urban studies. Today's cities focus mainly on roads, vehicles and commercial growth, while ignoring pedestrian-friendly spaces, environmental balance and traditional planning ideas seen in ancient temple towns. Because of this, we are facing problems like traffic, environmental damage, loss of heritage buildings, and unplanned development. In this we can study how once towns balanced social, economic and environmental needs and also help guide more in terms sustainable planning in modern cities.

1.3 Research Questions

The study is guided by the following research questions

- 1) How are temple towns spatially organised and how does this organization support social, economic and cultural activities?
- 2) What strategies were used for the environmental and climate- responsible design in town planning and architecture?
- 3) How does temple function as both economic and social hubs with these settlements?
- 4) What is the secret behind the long-term durability of the temple structure ?and materials used?
- 5) How does temple architecture contribute to natural cooling inside the temple?
- 6) How can we apply the sustainable design strategies used in ancient temple design?

2. Literature Review

2.1 Temple towns in Indian Urban History

Across India, we can see how many cities grew around the temple towns, and you can still see how these places look and work today. These communities form near major religious centres, where temple was more than the place of worship. Think of Madurai, Srirangam or Varanasi. How beautifully they were planned, the temples are always placed at the centre like a heart of the city, balancing with proper streets, markets, crafts as living this also shaped their living status .

Figure 2.1: Madurai Meenakshi Amman Temple (Source: Online)

Rituals linked with well-worn pilgrimage routes point to the same idea: religious practice helped make the layout and growth of these places. The presence of all these strongly influenced the formation and growth of these settlements.

2.2 Sacred Planning Concepts

In many texts, we have seen how sacred planning shaped temple complexes and towns that grew around them. Texts like Vastu Shastra layout special rules based on the concept of Vastu Purusha Mandala, it's a sacred grid said to mirror the order of the cosmos. And also the Gaya-Mandala (Gaya is a place). This practice of vastu shastra is still practiced today , builders set the orientation, zoning, and hierarchy of the spaces in a temple site, and at times also used to plan nearby streets and neighbourhoods. It is said that temples were placed in the cardinal directions (at the centre), and spaces formed in rings around them. Such special ordering often extended into the urban structure of temple towns.

Figure 2.2: Showing Gaya-Mandala (Source online)

3. Conceptual Framework

3.1 Sacred Spatial Planning

As we all know that India was famous for its Vedic knowledge, the town planning was also influenced by sacred ideas found in ancient texts such as Vedas, Puranas and Shilpa-Shastras. The Vastu Purusha Mandala is the

key concept, it represents the order of the universe. According to Vastu Shastra, Buildings and settlements are planned based on the cardinal directions-North, South, East and West, linked to the five natural elements (i.e Panchabhutas) – Air, Water, Fire, Space and

Earth. Using this system, temples were placed at the centre, with streets and other places around it.

The planning of town can be understood by two levels, Meso and Micro. The meso level focuses on the overall town structure, including how temples connects with main

streets, markets and other spaces etc. Major streets radiate from or circle the temple. The micro level looks at narrow streets, everyday spaces, these spaces also support daily worship, social interaction, local trade etc, creating a lively environment where religious, social and economic life come together.

Figure 3.1: Meso-Micro Level Structure of the spatial organization of Temple Town (Author's work)

4. Typology of Temple Town Planning

Vishwakarma is traditionally known as the divine architect and is believed to have spread the knowledge of the Shilpa-shastras. Even today, artisans worship him as a symbol of craftsmanship and creativity. The growth of town was largely influenced by the natural site conditions. Many of them were located along the banks of the river, near seashore, or near large lakes so that people can make much use of the water resources, and also worshipped them as gods. In ancient texts it is said that the overall layout of a town should be planned

first, and houses should be arranged afterwards. This concept is still practiced till today.

Another important text, the Mansara Shilpa-Shastra, explains different aspects of town planning soil conditions, wind direction, climate, building orientation for sunlight, and the role of topography. It also describes different town layouts such as Dandaka, Swastika, Padmaka (Lotus shaped), Nandyavarta (Flower shaped), Prastara, Chaturmukha, and Karmukha (Bow shaped). This shows how ancient Indian Planning combined environmental understanding with cultural and spiritual values while designing.

Figure 4: 7 Types of Temple Layouts (Source: Reference Book)

4.1 Concentric Temple Town Pattern

In this concentric patterns, the temple is placed at the centre of the town. Streets are built in layers around it. These streets are often used for temple processions and festivals. The area close to the temple usually has religious buildings, priests' houses, and small shops selling ritual items.

Example: Meenakshi Amman Temple, Madurai

Figure 4.1 : Concentric type layout (Source: Author's own work (GIS) & google map)

4.2 Axial Temple Town Pattern

In Axial pattern, a main street leads directly to the temple. The temple becomes the main focus at the end of the street. Shops and bazaars are usually placed along this route to serve pilgrims and visitors.

Example: Ramanathaswamy Temple, Rameswaram

Figure 4.2 : Axial type layout (Source:Author's own work(GIS) & google map))

4.3 Grid Based Temple Town Pattern

Some temples towns follow a grid based town pattern influenced by the traditional planning such as the vastu purusha mandala. In this layout, the streets cross each other at regular intervals, creating rectangular blocks for houses and shops. The temple is as usually placed in the center.

Example: Brihadeeswara Swamy Temple, Thanjavur

Figure 4.3 : Grid-Based Town layout (Source:Author's own work(GIS) & google map))

4.4 Pilgrimage-Oriented Spatial Pattern

In some towns, the planning is done based on the pilgrimage routes rather than a fixed geometric plan. Here streets connects temples, waterbodies, shrines and other sacred places. These paths are used by pilgrims for ritual and processions.

Example: Varanasi and the Kashi Vishwanath Temple

Figure 4.4 : Pilgrimage-Oriented Spatial town layouts of Kashi Vishwanath Temple Town (Source:Author's source)

4.5 Hybrid Temple Town Pattern

Combining all spatial patterns such as, grip, axial and concentric layouts makes the hybrid pattern. As the town grew and new activities emerged, the urban structure become more complex. However, the temple usually remains as the spatial centre of the town.

Example: Sri Ranganathaswamy Temple, Srirangam

Figure 4.5 : Hybrid Town layout (Source:Author's own work(GIS) & google map)

5. Case Study Analysis

This section looks at Srirangam-Ranganathaswamy Temple town to see how temples have affected the town's layout. It explains how temples influence the streets, marketplaces, and pilgrims movements in these settlements.

5.1 Srirangam- Ranganathaswamy Temple

5.1.1 Temple History

Srirangam is one of the most important Vishnu temples in Southern India. It is located beside the Kaveri river and dedicated to lord Ranganatha. The temple has been an important religious centre from many years and is closely connected to Sri Vaishnava tradition. According to History, the temple is related to Vibhishana, who is the brother of Ravana from Sri Lanka. After the Ramayanam , Lord Rama himself gifted him a sacred idol of Vishnu. While returning to Sri Lanka, Vibhisana rested on the island of Srirangam and placed the idol there.

Figure 5.1.1 : Old Srirangam (Source: online)

When he tried to take it again, it didn't move. From that day, the lord rested in that place only and because of him the place got its name as Srirangam. And Lord also promised Vibhishana that he will face south so that he could be worshipped from Sri Lanka itself. Because of this story, the temple faces south usually temples face east direction.

Historically, the temple was built as a small shrine but gradually grew in importance. Between the 5th and 9th centuries, the Tamil Vaishnava

5.1.2 Architecture (Street Networks, Processional Routes and Walkability Analysis)

The Srirangam temple is a remarkable example of South Indian temple architecture. The complex is arranged in seven rectangular enclosures that surround the main shrine. These layers are believed to represent the structure of the universe described in Hindu texts. Each enclosure has large entrance towers called gopurams. The temple complex covers more than sixty hectares, making it one of the largest temple complexes in India. The outer areas include houses, shops, smaller shrines, and religious residences, creating a lively temple town where priests, scholars, and devotees live and work. As visitors move inward, the spaces become more sacred and lead to the central shrine of Lord Ranganatha. Unlike most Hindu temples that face east, the Srirangam temple faces south because of the legend of Vibhishana. The southern entrance is the busiest part of the temple, with large gopurams, shops, and vendors selling flower garlands for worship. The tall gateway towers decorated with mythological figures are one of the most striking and admired features of the temple.

saints also known as the Alvars visited the temple and composed devotional hymns. Later, the scholar Nathamuni collected these hymns for temple worship. In the 11th and 12th centuries, the philosopher Ramanuja lived in Srirangam and helped strengthen the Sri Vaishnava tradition. Over time, rulers such as the Cholas, Pandyans, Vijayanagara Kings, and Nayakas supported and expanded the temple, making it one of the most important pilgrimage centres in India.

Figure 5.1.2.2 : Shown Srirangam market street (Source: Reference Book)

Gopurams are the main entrance to the sacred area, located in the fourth enclosure of Srirangam temple. Visitors remove their footwear prior to entry. Many small shrines are present in this area, honoring the Alvars, Acharyas & other important religious figures. In the past, this courtyard functioned as the outer space where individuals from diverse communities could worship. There are also some of the most beautiful structures in this temple complex. The northwest corner is home to the temple of the goddess Ranganayaki, which is a significant shrine. This structure is adorned with statues from the Chola period, which demonstrate how distinct shrines for the goddess were traditionally constructed in large temples.

Figure 5.1.2.1 : Srirangam Temple Plan (Source: Reference Book)

Another important structure in the fourth enclosure is the Thousand-Pillared Hall on the eastern side of the temple complex. It was built during the late Chola period and served as a large public space for gatherings and religious events. One of the most important activities held here is the Margali festival (December-January), when the four thousand Tamil devotional hymns are recited. In earlier times, when many people were not allowed to enter the inner sanctum, such public rituals were very important for worship. Near this courtyard, the Vijayanagar rulers later built a small eight-pillared hall decorated with sculptures of warriors on horses fighting wild animals. These carvings show the artistic style of that period. Another shrine in the fourth enclosure is the Krishna (Venugopala) temple on the southern side.

Figure 5.1.2.3 : Venugopala Swamy Entrance (Source: Reference Book)

It is known for its beautiful design and sculptures. The shrine was likely developed during the Nayaka period, and its walls are decorated with figures of women playing music and dancing. On the western side of the courtyard there is a lotus pond. During the spring festival, the temple deity is taken on a decorated boat across the pond, creating a joyful and lively celebration for the devotees.

The third enclosure of the Srirangam temple is partly open to the public, but many of the buildings here are used to prepare rituals for the main shrine. Near the southern entrance is a decorated pillared hall connected to the shrine of Garuda, the sacred eagle and vehicle of Lord Vishnu. This hall was built by the Nayaka rulers of Madurai in the 17th Century. On the western side are the large temple kitchens where offerings like dosai(dosa) and vadai(vada) are prepared for the deity and later given to devotees as prasad.

Figure 5.1.2.4 : Shows wall from 3rd enclosure & east entrance to 4th enclosure (Source: Reference Book)

5.1.3 Water and Environmental Systems

This enclosure also has two sacred water tanks: the Moon Tank in the northeast and the Sun Tank in the southeast, both used for ritual bathing. The Moon Tank is especially important during the Margali festival, when Tamil devotional hymns are recited. During this time, many devotees gather to watch the ceremonial bathing of the deity, creating a lively and festive atmosphere. The open space between the tanks is also used for other temple celebrations and activities, also contribute to the environmental and cultural landscape of the temple complex. Nayaka rulers of Madurai in the seventeenth century. On the western side are the large temple kitchens where offerings vadai(vada) are

5.1.5 urban planning

From a planning perspective, Srirangam represents a well-organized temple town. The temple is arranged in seven concentric rectangular enclosures called Prakaras surrounding the central shrine. These layers are linked by large gateway towers called gopurams. The outer areas include houses, shops, and small shrines, creating a lively temple town, while the inner spaces become more sacred as they lead to the main sanctum. This layout shows how religious ideas influenced both the architecture and the planning of the town.

prepared for the deity and later given to devotees as prasad.

5.1.4 Temple Economic Zones

Economic activities are closely connected to the daily life of the temple. Small shops selling flowers, garlands, and other ritual items are usually found near the entrances, especially around the busy southern gateway where most visitors enter. Inside the temple complex, large kitchens prepare food offerings for the deity, which are later shared with devotees as prasad. Festivals, pilgrimages, and regular temple visits also provide opportunities for local vendors and workers, helping support the livelihoods of people living around the temple.

Figure 1 Figure 5.1.5.1 : entrance to Rangavilasa Mandapa in 4th enclosure & Garuda Mandapa of ornate Pillars decorated with sculptures. (Source: Reference Book)

The diagram highlights a buffer area around the Sri Ranganathaswamy Temple using QGIS , showing the main influence zone of the temple within the town. Inside this area, the street network follows a clear hierarchy. Wide main streets run around the temple's concentric enclosures and act as important processional routes during festivals, connecting the major temple gates (gopurams). From these primary streets, smaller secondary streets extend into residential and market areas, while narrow lanes serve the local neighbourhoods. This organized street pattern shows how the planning of Srirangam was shaped by religious activities while also supporting everyday movement and settlement.

6. How these strategies can be applied in present design concepts

Traditional temple towns in India show how religion, architecture, and urban planning were closely linked in everyday life. These towns were not built only as places of worship; they were also designed to support daily activities, community interaction, and local trade. The way these settlements were planned helped create comfortable living environments while also responding to the local climate. Even today, these traditional planning ideas provide useful lessons for creating more sustainable and people-friendly cities.

In present, walkability (compact neighbourhoods, safe pedestrian streets, easily accessible public spaces) these will help and support people to use less vehicles and walk more. By re-introducing rain water harvesting systems, maintaining urban ponds, and some works like re-charge underground water, can help conserve water and support a more sustainable and environmentally urban development. We can make more of local markets, cultural areas, so that the area remains more active. Another best method is traditional cooling, which can still inspire modern architecture. By using features such as natural ventilation, open courtyards, shaded spaces, and buildings.

7. Conclusion

Temple towns such as Srirangam show how traditional Indian settlements successfully combined religion, architecture, and urban planning. The temple complex, along with its surrounding streets, markets, and homes, created a well-organized environment where social, cultural, and economic activities were closely connected. Features like walkable streets, temple tanks, shaded spaces, and open courtyards helped make the town safe for people.

These traditional planning ideas still offer valuable lessons for modern cities. Concepts such as walkable neighbourhoods, mixed land use, water management, and climate-responsive design are now considered important for sustainable urban development. By studying temple towns like Srirangam, planners and architects can learn how to create cities that are not only functional but also environmentally responsible and culturally meaningful.

8. References

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